

Synthetic, Structural, Thermal and Electrical Studies of some Coordination Polymers

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The polyschiff base ligand DDBPD derived from 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl and 1,3-propanediamine, forms solid polychelates of the type $[M(DDBPD).nH_2O]_n$ with bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu. They have been characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic and spectral data. The results of thermal and electrical conductivity studies have been presented.

COORDINATION polymers having good thermal stability and catalytic activity have enhanced the development of polymeric materials either from polymeric or monomeric ligands. This communication describes the preparation and characterisation of the chelates prepared from the ligand DDBPD derived from 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl and 1,3-propanediamine with bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, and Cu.

Experimental

All the metal acetates and chemicals used were of A. R. grade. All the solvents were purified by distillation.

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl (DDABP): It was prepared by a known method¹. To a hot solution of DDABP (0.2 mol) in dry ethanol (50 ml) was added with stirring a solution of 1,3-propanediamine (0.1 mol) in dry ethanol. The mixture was refluxed at 83–87° for about 4 h and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting dark yellow crystals were washed several times with dry ethanol and air-dried, m.p. 191°. It was found insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF.

Preparation of chelates: Equimolar proportions of the metal acetate and DDBPD dissolved separately in minimum quantity (25–50 ml) of DMF, filtered and then mixed in hot condition with stirring. It was refluxed at 128° for 5–6 h. The resulting coloured solid was washed successively with DMF, dry ethanol and acetone and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl₂. Iron(II) acetylacetonate was used for the synthesis of the Fe^{II} chelate. All the complexes were dark coloured solid and insoluble in common organic solvents.

Elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurement at room temperature, diffuse reflectance and ir spectra were done to characterise the complexes. The thermogravimetric results were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 analyser with TADS computer system with heating rate 10° min⁻¹. The electrical resistivity was measured on a BPL (India), RM 160 MK IIIA instrument.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data (Table 1) are of the polychelates correspond to the general formula ML or [ML]_n.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)				% loss ≤ 150°
		C	H	N	M	
DDBPD	Yellow	74.31 (74.02)	6.73 (6.49)	10.05 (9.10)	—	—
[Mn ^{II} (DDBPD)2H ₂ O] _n	Gulf red	57.44 (58.01)	4.53 (4.64)	7.05 (7.13)	13.60 (13.78)	10.10
[Fe ^{II} (DDBPD)2H ₂ O] _n	Golden brown	57.19 (57.26)	4.51 (4.56)	7.02 (7.15)	14.04 (14.21)	11.10
[(Co ^{II} (DDBPD)]2H ₂ O] _n	Spectral leaf	57.00 (58.06)	4.50 (4.78)	7.00 (7.06)	14.72 (14.95)	7.98
[Ni ^{II} (DDBPD)]H ₂ O] _n	Brown	59.57 (59.85)	5.22 (5.28)	7.31 (5.56)	15.34 (15.44)	4.50
[(Cu ^{II} (DDBPD)]2H ₂ O] _n	Grey	56.22 (57.08)	4.93 (5.14)	6.90 (6.98)	15.60 (16.09)	9.70

The presence of strong band at 1560 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$)² in the ligand spectrum shifted to higher wavenumbers in the spectra of the polychelates, which suggests the strong bonding of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group with metal ion^{3,4}. The medium intensity broad band of the ligand at $3070\text{--}3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH) with intramolecular hydrogen bonding^{5,6} disappeared in the complexes indicating metal-oxygen bond formation². The phenolic $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band of the ligand (1200 cm^{-1})² shifted to higher wavenumber on complexation indicating protonation through OH group. All the polychelates revealed weak to medium intensity broad band at $3300\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and weak band around 780 cm^{-1} due to coordinated water^{7,8}. All the polychelates showed bands at $510\text{--}600$ (M-O) and $500\text{--}440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-N)^{7,9}.

In the diffuse reflectance spectra, the Mn^{II} complex showed some novel features of interest and exhibits the transition sextet-quartet for the ${}^6A_1(g)$ ground term. It exhibited three weak bands at 22.22, 19.23 and 11.62 kK in an octahedral environment¹⁰ due to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, ${}^4E_g(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ and C.T. respectively. The Fe^{II} polymer exhibited bands at 10.30–11.62 and 15.87–20.83 kK assigned to transition ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ and C.T. respectively. The bands in this region are characteristic of Fe^{II} high-spin octahedral complex¹¹. The calculated¹² crystal field parameters $Dq=1063\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B=575\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta=0.54$ and $C=2300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are also in favour of octahedral geometry to the Fe^{II} polychelate which is consistent that reported by Bhawe *et al.*¹³. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of Co^{II} -DDBPD exhibited two bands at 9.52–16.66 kK which may be assigned to transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively for tetrahedral geometry¹⁴. Different crystal field parameters have been calculated using the known relation¹⁵. A broad band found at 9.52–10.60 kK, is due to lower symmetry field¹⁶. The values of $10Dq$ and B for the Co^{II} polymer has been calculated from the observed ν_2 and ν_3 following the ligand field theory of spin-allowed transition¹⁷. Making the use of $\mu_{\text{obs}}=3.87$ ($l=4\lambda/10D$), the spin-orbit coupling constant for the Co^{II} -DDBPD has been evaluated¹⁸. The lower value of λ (-66 cm^{-1}) for the Co^{II} polychelate suggests the significant orbital overlapping. The diffused reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} -DDBPD polychelate show two bands at 18.51–22.72 kK due to transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$. Appearance of the bands near visible region indicate their square-planar nature¹⁹, which is supported by its diamagnetic nature²⁰. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate shows two bands in their normally expected region for square-planar Cu^{II} complexes⁴. The bands at 11.62 and 13.69–15.62 kK are assigned to transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ respectively. These bands may be due to $d-d$ transition which suggests the square-planar stereochemistry²¹. The broadness of the band may be an indication towards lower symmetry.

The Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes lost water near $160\text{--}200^\circ$, the weight-losses corresponding to two

molecular coordinated water molecules per repeating unit. The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes lost water at $120\text{--}140^\circ$, which are probably crystal water²². The observed weight-loss is a little higher than that required and this may be due to some other chain degradation reactions involved in pyrolysis of the coordination polymer²². The decomposition temperature of the polychelates decreases in the order: $\text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Fe} > \text{Mn} > \text{Cu}$. The analysis of thermograms indicates that the polychelates decompose in two stages after the loss of water molecules, the first step being rapid as compared to the second one. Decomposition is completed at about 700° . Thermodynamic parameters^{23,24} for all the complexes were found to be nearly the same, which indicates a common reaction mode²⁵.

The electrical conductivity of the complexes at 100° fall in the order: $\text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{Fe} > \text{Co}$, and their activation energy increases in the order: $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Fe} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn}$. Over the whole temperature range, the values of the electrical conductivity were between 10^{-6} and $10^{-11}\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1). The difference in the electrical conductivity of the complexes arises mainly due to the difference in chemical structure. In case of the Mn^{II} polymers the electrical conductivity is not that varying as compared to other metal ion polychelates, which

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of complexes: (a) Mn^{II} -DDBPD, (b) Fe^{II} -DDBPD, (c) Co^{II} -DDBPD, (d) Ni^{II} -DDBPD and (e) Cu^{II} -DDBPD.

may be due to existence of Mn^{II} ion high-spin (d^5) electronic configuration.

The tentative structure of the complexes is as follows :

$M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} . For Co, Ni and Cu complexes the coordinated H_2O molecules should be absent.

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References

1. A. L. WILD, C. H. SHUNK and C. H. HOFFMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1733.
2. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3781.
3. K. G. WARRIER, P. N. MOHANDAS and P. J. JOSEPH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 628.
4. A. M. KARAMPURWALA, R. P. PATEL and J. R. SHAH, *Angew. Makromol. Chem.*, 1980, **87**, 87.
5. H. H. FREEDMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2900.
6. H. A. TIJMIR, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 723.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
8. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", 1962, p. 218.
9. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967, p. 319.
10. L. J. HEIST, G. F. KOSTER and A. M. JOHNSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **80**, 6471.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
12. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 545.
13. N. S. BHAVE and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 244.
14. M. N. PATEL and S. H. PATIL, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1982, **17**, 675.
15. C. J. BALHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962.
16. J. D. NAVRATIL and S. S. ZUMDAHL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2191.
17. R. L. CARLIN, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1963, **40**, 135.
18. B. N. FIGGIS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 1553.
19. B. T. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 682.
20. H. C. RAI, R. V. SHARMA and R. S. THAKUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 9457.
21. L. D. DAVE, H. K. KOTHARI and P. SUDHAM-SHUMOULL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 771.
22. R. M. JOSHI and M. M. PATEL, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1983, **19**, 919.
23. E. FREEMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 394.
24. J. B. SHARP and S. A. WENTWORTH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 2060.
25. J. G. LEIPOLDT and H. MEYER, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 1361.
26. V. NIKOLAEV, V. A. LOGVIENKO and L. I. MYACHINA, *Thermal Anal.*, 1969, **2**, 779.